

Social Media Usage, Addiction and Its Impact on Academic Performance Among Students: A Narrative Review

Subha Lakshmi V S¹, Dr. K. Anbu²

¹Ph.D Research Scholar, Dept of Social Work, Pondicherry University, India

²Assistant Professor, Dept of Social Work, Pondicherry University, India

Corresponding Author Email: subhasureash29@gmail.com

Abstract— The increasing usage of social media platforms among youth is a developing worry, and their usage of social media may negatively impact their academic performance, social life, and mental health. Social media networks are known for its access to knowledge because of the amazing advancements in technology. Such platforms also pave way for the youth to be influenced way too much. This takes a toll on their psychological and physiological health. The young people take them up a notch in changing their physical appearance and manipulating their surroundings to the standards of social media appearance. This paper attempts to comprehensively examine the multifaceted impact on academic performance by meticulously going over the existing literature that currently exists about the relationship between social media use and addiction of social media, this paper is purely on the basis of second-hand information from various studies conducted. The paper also attempts to provide future recommendations for the improvement of the youth's academic performance with the adaptations to the emergence of new technologies.

Keywords – Social media platform, Addiction, Students, Youth, Academic performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media is a platform that encourages a sense of participation among the users who can create a user profile in the social media platforms such Facebook and Instagram (Manning, 2014). Social media has become an inseparable part of our daily lives. Social media is the platform that give individuals the opportunity to interact, using two-way communication; meaning, that anyone who has online accounts can share their opinions with other social media users (El-Badawy T, 2015). It has made communication and information sharing easier than ever before, and teenagers are among the most active users of social media. To begin with, social media is a platform that helps larger number of populations to connect with their family, friends and peers. Anyone can easily communicate and stay in touch with their friends and family, regardless of their location.

In the last ten years, the online world has changed, thanks to the invention of social media, everyone now exchanges emotions, ideas, feelings, personal information, videos and pictures (Dhiman, 2022). Social media also enables teenagers to expand their social circle and connect with like-minded individuals, which can be beneficial for their personal and professional growth. Other than Social media, from the last two years, several online platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom and Google Meet are preferred to organize any kind of virtual meetings, webinars and online classes (Sharma S, 2022). Approximately 3.5 billion people worldwide, or 82% of the developed world's population and 35% of the developing world's population, used computers and smartphones to access the Internet in 2016 (Masthi, 2018).

Moreover, social media can serve as a source of entertainment and relaxation for teenagers. They can watch funny videos, memes, and other entertaining content that can help them unwind after a long day of schoolwork or extracurricular activities. However, there are also several drawbacks of social media usage among teenagers. Social networking addiction is a mental devotion, apportionment of time and resources to social networking platforms deserting other educational, and professional activities (Ndubuaku* V, 2020). Smith et al., (2020) found that there are negative consequences on academic performance, social relationships, and mental health associated with teenagers' increased use of social media platforms.

The arise of social media platforms as a tool for education is critical. The social media sites such as Facebook has emerged as a tool of collaborative learning in educational settings, when Facebook is used with addition to other tools it promotes the collaborative learning, paves way for the students to have conversations with one another, exchanging knowledge and information (Hamid et al., 2018). Likewise, YouTube has gained its position as a valuable resource for education, the teachers, instructors and YouTubers in general uploads their video content in their respective page with variety of content visually, with that the students will be able to comprehend and understand any concepts known to human kind. LinkedIn being a professional

site for career growth and development has proved itself with academic advancement, the students may use LinkedIn to hear the professional opinions and gather information that might be useful for their career advancement.

In addition to psychological effects like anxiety, insomnia, exhaustion, loneliness, and depression, early-life addiction can have a negative impact on a person's physical health, including problems with the brain, hearing, eyes, and heart. It can also have a social impact on problems like relationship problems, social isolation, and academic decline. (Masthi, 2018). Excessive usage of social media can lead to a sedentary lifestyle, which can increase the risk of obesity and other health problems. Additionally, prolonged exposure to the blue light emitted by electronic devices can disrupt sleep patterns, leading to insomnia and other sleep-related disorders.

II. SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE AMONG STUDENTS

Today's youth are particularly prone to using social media. According to the research conducted by Pew Research Center Study (2018), Most of the young adults ranging from the 18 to 29 years are known to use at least one social media platform such as Facebook, Twitter and Snapchat. The majority of students tend to think that social media is very beneficial for learning, studying, researching, and discovering information. Students are susceptible to persuasion. Because of their curiosity, they desire to investigate or attempt what is brand-new and popular in order to blend in with society. In addition to books and other academically related materials, mobile phones have become a necessary component of every student's life. The primary reason for using social media among students has been found out to be information sharing (Sharma A, 2016). Among the students the efficiency and convenience of the sharing of information on social media has been the number one reason for the usage.

Beyond only conversations, social media has a significant impact on how young people receive information. Anderson and Jiang's (2018) study look at how Americans use social media to consume news, concentrating on younger audiences. The survey finds that adolescents mostly obtain their news via social media, particularly from sites like Facebook and Twitter. According to Junco (2015), among the students the social media has been viewed as an easily accessible and practical for information sharing in terms of academic interests, extracurricular activities or their personal interest. This is possible because of the presence of social media like Facebook, twitter and Instagram, creating a virtual world of connectedness. The students utilise social media sites like LinkedIn and Twitter to keep up with current research trends, follow academic updates, and engage in debates which can be advantageous for their academics (Manca, 2016). Social media gives students a platform to engage with peers, instructors, and subject matter experts in their profession, and its function in promoting cooperation and knowledge sharing has become essential to the academic experience. The students also utilize the social media for their collaborative learning and research. The students use these online platforms and forums for blogging their academic interests, share thoughts, connect with like-minded people.

Social media's dynamic and visually engaging qualities greatly affect students' attraction and engagement. Students may access and enjoy helpful information in more engaging formats, including lectures, infographics, and interactive postings, thanks to platforms like YouTube and Instagram. The social media's interactive features and eye-catching aesthetics increase students' desire to engage in learning conversations and activities (Junco, 2015). One important component influencing how young people use social media is peer influence. Peer influence on online behaviour is emphasised in a study by O'Keeffe and Clarke-Pearson (2016) that explores the effects of social media on kids and teenagers. Youth's behaviour on social media is greatly influenced by their peers. Online safety and privacy are major issues among young people who use social media so frequently. In order to secure personal information, encourage responsible online behaviour, and address concerns connected to cyberbullying and internet harassment, research highlights the necessity of education and awareness programmes (Livingstone et al., 2017).

The penetration of social media and smartphones have drastically increased among the Indian population, in research conducted by Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI, 2021) found that around 376 billion people in India uses social media with the greater percentage belonging to students. The relationship of social media with students in India was studied by Rani and Rao (2016), revealing the transformation in social dynamics with the rise to usage of social media among students. There is a strong bond between the usage of social network and college students in India, in the 21st century (Moradgholi et al, 2018)

III. SOCIAL MEDIA AND RISK OF ADDICTION

The uncontrolled usage of internet among students have increased significantly, arising problems in daily life tasks led from the problematic use of computer or technology (Choudhury & Ali, 2020). The young people tend to maintain an online appearance more often than older people which can be addictive (Zhao J et al., 2022). The key indicators of the addictive nature of social

media platforms identified by Andreassen et al. (2016) were preoccupation, withdrawal, tolerance, and conflict. The social media addiction and other behavioural addictions shares similarities with each other.

The causes of the social media addiction can be vast including psychological factors, social factors and environmental factors. Individuals with personality problems such as low self-esteem, overthinking, irritability and impulsiveness could turn to social media as a coping mechanism for online connections and validation (Andreassen et al., 2016). Social media addiction has consequences that go beyond a simple infatuation with social networking sites; these include withdrawal symptoms, heightened tolerance necessitating longer engagements, and conflicts stemming from choosing virtual relationships over in-person obligations. The people with psychological issues including anxiety and depression can also turn to social media as a means to escape the reality and negative thoughts, falling into addictive behaviours (Primack et al., 2017).

Social networking platforms' addictive qualities frequently resemble other behavioural addictions, with several significant parallels. Understanding these similarities is essential to understanding the wider range of addictive behaviours connected to technology and online interactions. People may unknowingly display addictive tendencies and behaviours similar to those seen in traditional types of addiction as they grow more and more immersed in virtual places. The social factors such as peer pressure and social comparison can evoke addiction of social media among individuals. Peers play a major role in fostering addictive behaviours, where the individuals are pressurized to conform to the trends and social norms (Kuss et al., 2017). According to Fardouly et al. (2015), addictive tendencies might be fuelled by a continual comparison with others. Availability of smartphones in every hand has made the access to technology easier than ever.

Along with the technological accessibility comes the risk of obsessive and chronic addiction of social media usage (Primack et al., 2017). These social networking platforms are purposefully designed to gain their attention and lure the users into the virtual world. The social networking platforms' features such as notifications, likes, comments and its loops encourage the addictive behaviours (Andreassen et al., 2016). According to Choudhury and Ali (2020), excessive internet use can lead to a variety of problems that can interfere with many facets of everyday duties. These difficulties might show up in the social, personal, or intellectual aspects and affect one's general well-being. The negative uses of technology and computers highlights the necessity of a thoughtful approach to integrating technology into daily life, especially for younger generation.

Younger generation seem to be more likely to maintain a constant online appearance, according to Zhao J et al. (2022) who highlighted the age-related component of internet usage trends. Because the appeal of the digital world becomes more alluring than interactions in real life, this greater involvement may result in addictive behaviours. It is essential to comprehend these age-related variations in order to customise educational initiatives and interventions meant to encourage safe internet usage across various age groups.

The addictive behaviours of social media likely possess drastic impact in the well-being including physical, mental and social consequences. The significant physical health consequences list to obesity due to lack of movement, vision issues, hearing issues, lack of alertness and sleep disturbances. The use of social media ties the individual down to sedentary position lacking in other activities. Indefinite amount of time spent on social media accounts for the lack of physical activities among the users arising the condition of obesity (Primack et al., 2017). The sedentary life style caused due to social media overuse not only brings forth the issue of obesity but also raises concern for the overall health and arises the importance of regular exercise (Chin et al., 2019). The excessive use of digital devices also puts a strain to the eye leading to headache, blurry vision and pain in the eyes (Rosenfield, 2016).

Anxiety and depression are common mental problems faced by the generation of social media users. The impulsive social media usage will be directly associated with the increased levels of depression and anxiety (Primack et al., 2017). The prolonged use of social media, especially before bed and right after waking from bed are directly linked to sleep disturbances among the users. This habitual condition can worsen the sleep schedule and collapse mental health conditions among the users in general (Primack et al., 2017).

The excessive use of social media tends people to cut off their ties with the reality, the family, friends and everything they know in the real world submerging themselves in the virtual world, which from the study by Kuss and Griffiths (2017) explained that social media addiction and loneliness is directly correlated to each other. Prioritising online connections over in person relationship can lead to the human relationships neglect and individuals alleviate themselves from the reality (Andreassen et al., 2016). These social media connections foster comparison and the demand for the need for validation and feeling inadequate often (Fardouly et al., 2015).

IV. SOCIAL MEDIA IMPACT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Social media usage among teenagers has both advantages and disadvantages. While it can serve as a platform for communication, entertainment, and creativity, it can also have a negative impact on mental health, academic performance, and physical well-being. As parents and educators, it is essential to monitor and guide teenagers' social media usage, ensuring that they use it responsibly and in moderation. By striking a balance between social media usage and other aspects of their lives, students can harness the benefits of social media for their academic achievement and accomplishment while avoiding its potential pitfalls.

However, the social media usage among students, have crucial negative impact on their academic performance as well. Social media used in the educational field is primarily to share information with students, collect data for research projects, share academic interests with a larger audience, interact with students, and learn about their viewpoints during interaction (L. Zhao, 2023). With the ease of access to social media, teenagers can get easily distracted from their studies, leading to a decline in academic performance. Social media can also promote a culture of instant gratification, which can make it challenging for teenagers to focus on long-term goals and delayed gratification.

While the debate on the whether the impact of social media on academics is positive or negative still in the talks, the social media usage among the students has proven to be boon for their academics as it's also on the other proven to be bane for their overall well-being. On the positive note, the students actively participate in academic activities and improving their knowledge using the social media platforms showing higher levels in academic performance (Junco, 2015). The social media connections and usage also proven to be beneficial for students to communicate effectively with their peers and their instructors, showing significant improvement in the academic performance of the students and improved level of satisfaction in the education (Manca S, 2016).

The social media platforms have transformed to the extent of providing educational information in the forms of educational lectures, tutorials and study materials, which the students greatly use to improve their academic performance and skills. The creation of online communities explicitly for the academics have significantly helped the students to be proficient in academics, the communities have also provided support to the students by the peers and creating a sense of belonging among them (Dabbagh N, 2019). These communities help the students to have healthy discussions, insights and academic encouragement, which enables a favourable influence on academic performance. The usage of social media platforms has the students explore the doors of opportunity in career development and networking with the professionals. The students have found to be using networking sites such as LinkedIn improving their academic and professional expertise.

It is found in a study the Egyptian students spend about 1 hour to 6 hours a day in social media platforms, like Facebook and google sites (El-Badawy T, 2015). In another study after half a decade it was found out that the students have moved to WhatsApp and YouTube as their most used social media platforms which is followed by Instagram and Facebook (Sharma S, 2022). The students using the above said social media platforms shows reduced GPA's indicating poor academic performance (Junco R, 2015). The study by Junco R (2015) shows the detrimental relationship between social media and academics of students. Students may choose these social media platforms and connections than their academic obligations due to procrastination.

It can be seen that the students with the excessive use of social media are more inclined to procrastination, given less importance to their academic obligations. These habits tend the students to dive into poor time management and putting off tasks that needs attention (Krischner, 2016). Social media may be used by some students as a coping strategy to momentarily escape the pressures of their academic obligations. Scrolling through social media might be an unhelpful way to release tension and take one's mind off of important work. Academic responsibilities can sometimes be eclipsed by the appeal of social media alerts, entertainment, and continuous connectedness. When students choose the instant gratification of social media over the gradual satisfaction of finishing assignments, procrastination develops into a habit. Social media engagements can lead to a mistaken view of time due to their immersive nature. Students may misjudge how much time they spend on social sites, unintentionally ignoring the responsibilities of their academic schedules. Students who are constantly exposed to information and impulses on social media may experience cognitive fatigue, which will hinder their ability to manage their time well. Continuous digital involvement can lead to a reduction in cognitive resources, which can impair an individual's ability to maintain concentration on academic work for an extended period of time.

According to the study conducted by Woods and Scott (2016), the increased use of social media leads to sleep deprivation among the students, especially at the bed time, this can cause memory consolidation, cognitive function and the academic performance in general. Students frequently spend extended periods of time on social media platforms, which are meant to be immersive and engaging, reading through feeds, watching videos, or taking part in online discussions. These late-night interactions might easily

go on longer due to the appeal of notifications and updates. When people use smartphones and tablets to access social media, they are exposing themselves to blue light emissions. Because blue light can inhibit melatonin synthesis and postpone the beginning of sleep, it can have a particularly negative impact on the circadian rhythm, which controls the sleep-wake cycle. Extended usage of social media before going to bed is linked to sleep disturbances. The continuous stimulation from digital screens is a factor in trouble sleeping, nighttime awakenings, and a decline in the sleep duration.

The students may also encounter cyberbullying, online harassment, or exclusion of social media leading to impact on mental health of the students, the psychological impact of cyberbullying will have serious effects on the student's capacity to concentrate on other things especially academics, the ability to have a casual conversation with their peers and finally altogether reflecting on their academic performance (Patchin, 2018). The emotional health of students may suffer significantly as a result of cyberbullying. People may be more willing to engage in behaviours they may not otherwise in person due to the anonymity and distance provided by online platforms. Increased tension, worry, and even sadness is just a few of the psychological effects of cyberbullying that might appear.

Social media platforms being the space for sharing, the achievements, accomplishment and the appealing lifestyle of their peers increase the sense of comparative stress and inferiority among the students (Tondoc et al, 2015). The continuous exposure to these academic accomplishment and achievements hinders the sense of feeling inadequate and paves way to social comparison and make the self-esteem deteriorate, which can lead to higher stress and weakened self-confidence of the students (Andreassen et al., 2016). The student's memory for knowledge has been severely impacted by multitasking of the social media and academic tasks at the same time. This loss of memory for knowledge can be directly linked to the poorer performance in the academics (Sana et al., 2017).

V. HEALTHY USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA FOR ACADEMIC ADVANCEMENT

Social media's continuous impact on students' life calls for a thoughtful approach to its use, one that prioritises productivity and academic advancement. the goal is to enable students to use social media as a means for academic advancement by offering reliable guidance. Parental and child dialogue on social media use should be encouraged.

Parental Guidance and Early Monitoring: Primack et al. (2017) assert that early parental monitoring and assistance are essential for fostering good internet behaviours. Parental intervention at an early age fosters a healthy parent-child relationship and helps children grasp the advantages and disadvantages of social media. It also helps lay the groundwork for safe online behaviour.

Pedagogical Considerations for Teachers: A careful approach to pedagogy is needed for the successful incorporation of social media sites into instructional activities. Teachers' ought to think about coordinating platform use with particular learning goals, offering advice on ethical platform use, and encouraging a balance between formal and informal learning opportunities (Junco et al., 2015).

Online Safety and Privacy: Youth use of social media is so common that worries about online safety and privacy are warranted. Studies underscore the necessity of education and awareness campaigns to encourage responsible online conduct, safeguard personal data, and tackle concerns pertaining to cyberbullying as well as internet abuse (Livingstone et al., 2017).

Media Literacy programs: Proactive measures to mitigate the problems arising from social media use have included the suggestion of media literacy programmes. Research highlights how critical thinking abilities are developed in kids through the integration of media literacy instruction into school curriculum, enabling them to properly navigate the digital realm (Hobbs, 2017).

Changing with the Times: The difficulties posed by social media use also change as the platforms themselves develop. The influence of changing social media trends on teenagers is examined in Twenge and Campbell's (2018) study, which highlights the necessity of flexible instructional approaches.

Creating an Organised Digital Schedule: Students may better manage their time by scheduling certain times for social media participation and academic work when they establish an organised digital schedule. This guarantees that productive study hours and downtime are balanced.

Using Educational information: To support their studies, students can make use of the educational information that is readily available on social media platforms. Participating in pertinent organisations, keeping up with academic conversations, and subscribing to educational channels all enhance the learning process.

Limiting Your Use of Social Media: Students must put limits on their use of social media because of the risk of addiction. A good balance may be preserved by setting time restrictions, making use of productivity tools, and exercising caution when consuming content.

Setting Academic Priorities: Students can better prioritise their studies by being made aware of the significance of deadlines and academic duties. The possibility of social media influencing their academic performance might be reduced by establishing specific objectives and deadlines.

VI. DISCUSSION

The social media usage among the students has a significant impact on the students' academic performance both positively and negatively. With the prevalence of social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and YouTube the learning ability and skills of the students seen to be improving and aids in the positive impact on the academic performance. Although the excessive or uncontrolled use of social media is also seen to be leading to addiction negatively impacts the academics of the students. With various social media variables such as video watching, media sharing, internet searching, and video gaming capturing students' attention for study such factors of social media, affects the academic performance of the students. With the preventive and healthy use habits of social media the student population can greatly improve their academic.

BIBLIOGRAPHY AND REFERENCES

1. Anuradha A. Ename, Vijay M. Rakhade, Lowlesh N. Yadav (2022). *A study on Positive and Negative Effects of Social Media on Society*. International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering
2. Avula Sahithi, Shailaja V Mane, Sharad Agarkhedkar (2019). *Use of Social Media and its Effects in School Going Adolescents*. Indian Journal of Youth and Adolescent Health.
3. Barbara Kieslinger (2015). *Academic peer pressure in social media: Experiences from the heavy, the targeted and the restricted user*. First Monday.
4. Brian A Primack, Ariel Shensa, Jaime E Sidani, Erin O Whaite, Liu Yi Lin, Daniel Rosen, Jason Colditz, Ana Radovic, Elizabeth Miller, E. (2017). *Social media use and perceived social isolation among young adults in the U.S*. American Journal of Preventive Medicine, 53 (1), 1-8.
5. Cecilie Schou Andreassen, Stale Pallesen, Mark D Griffiths, (2016). *The relationship between addictive use of social media, narcissism, and self-esteem: Findings from a large national survey*. Addictive Behaviors, 287-293.
6. Daria J. Kuss, Mark D. Griffiths, (2017). *Social networking sites and addiction: Ten lessons learned*. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 14 (3), 311.
7. Dr. Abid Ali, Bharat (2020). *Influence of Social Media in Developing Social Anxiety: A study of Kurukshetra University Students*. PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt / Egyptology.
8. Dr. Bharat Dhiman (2022). *Use and Impact of Social Media on Academic Performance of Kurukshetra University Students: A Case Study*. SSRN Electronic Journal.
9. Edson C. Tondoc Jr, Patrick Ferrucci, Margaret Duffy (2015). *Facebook use, envy, and depression among students: Is facebook depressing*. Computers in Human Behaviour.
10. Fausto Giunchiglia, Mattia Zeni, Elisa Gobbi, Enrico Bignotti, Ivano Bison (2018). *Mobile Social media usage and academic performance*. Computers in Human Behaviour.
11. Gwenn Schurgin O'Keeffe, Kathleen Clarke-Pearson (2016). *The impact of social media on children, adolescents, and families*. Pediatrics, 127 (4), 800-804.
12. Harikumar Pallathadka, Laxmi Kirana Pallathadka and Shoraisam Kiranbhala Devi (2022). *Reasons of Social Media Addiction among Youth: An Exploratory Study*. Integrated Journal for Research in Arts and Humanities (PP. 137-143).
13. Heather Cleland Woods, Holly Scott, (2016, January). *#Sleepyteens: Social media use in adolescence is associated with poor sleep quality, anxiety, depression and low self-esteem*. Journal of Behavioral Optometry.
14. Jasmine Fardouly, Phillippa C. Diedrichs, Lenny R. Vartanian, Emma Halliwell, (2015). *Social comparisons on social media: The impact of Facebook on young women's body image concerns and mood*. Body Image, 13, 38-45.
15. Jean M. Twenge, W. Keith Campbell (2018). *Associations between screen time and lower psychological well-being among children and adolescents: Evidence from a population-based study*. Preventive Medicine Reports, 12, 271-283.
16. Jimmie Manning (2014.) *Social media, definition and classes of*. In K. Harvey (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of social media and politics* (pp. 1158-1162). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
17. Justin W. Patchin, Sameer Hinduja, (2018). *Digital self-harm among adolescents*. Journal of Adolescent Health, 63(5), 579-583.

18. Joginder Goet (2022). *Impact of Social media on Academic performance of Students*. KIC International Journal of Social Science and Management.
19. Paul Kirschner, & Aryn C. Karpinski, (2016). *Facebook ® and academic performance*. Computers in Human Behavior, 59, 374-380.
20. Lei Zhao (2023). *Social Media Addiction and Its Impact on College Students' Academic Performance: The Mediating Role of Stress*. Asia-Pacific Education Researcher, 32(1), 81–90.
21. Maria Choudhury, Arif Ali (2020). *Social media addiction among youth: a gender comparison*. The international Journal of Indian Psychology.
22. Mark Rosenfield (2016). *Computer vision syndrome (a.k.a. digital eye strain)*. Optometry in practice.
23. Mehdi Akbari, Mohammad Hossein Bahadori, Salar Khanbabaei, Bahman Boruki Milan, Shiva Jamshidi, Marc N. Potenza (2023). Potential risk and protective factors related to problematic social media use among adolescents in Iran: A latent profile analysis.
24. Mohammed Habes 1,2, Mahmoud Alghizzawi 1, Rifat Khalaf 2, Said A. Salloum, Mazuri Abd. Ghani (2018). The relationship between Social Media and Academic Performance: Facebook perspective. International Journal of Information Technology and Language Studies.
25. Monica Anderson, Jingjing Jiang, (2018). *Teens, Social Media & Technology 2018*. Pew Research Center.
26. Morteza Moradgholi, Mohammad Hadi Mansour Lakoorej (2018). *Usage of Social networking websites among Undergraduate students*. IAU International Journal of Social Sciences.
27. Nada Dabbagh, Anastasia Kitsantas, (2012). *Personal learning environments, social media, and self-regulated learning: A natural formula for connecting formal and informal learning*. The Internet and Higher Education, 15 (1), 3-8.
28. N R Ramesh Masthi, Pruthvi S, Phaneendra Mallekavu (2018). *A comparative study on social media addiction between public and private high school students of urban Bengaluru, India*. ASEAN Journal of Psychiatry, Vol. 18 (2).
29. Pew Research Center. (2018). Social Media Use in 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2018/03/01/social-media-use-in-2018/>
30. Raktim Engti, Mohmmedirfan H. Momin, Shailee N. Vyas (2022). *Social media addiction and its impact among the school students during COVID-19 lockdown in an urban area of Western India: a cross-sectional study*. International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences.
31. Renee Hobbs (2017). *The digital and media literacy (DML) movement in the United States: Response to the fake news panic*. Journal of Media Literacy Education, 9(2), 71-75.
32. Reynol Junco, Greg Heiberger, Eric Loken (2015). *The effect of Twitter on college student engagement and grades*. Journal of Computer Assisted Learning, 31 (3), 220-232.
33. Reynol Junco (2015). *Engaging students through social media: Evidence-based practices for use in student affairs*. John Wiley & Sons.
34. Saritha S R, Mr. Baskar B, Shreya Khandelwal, Shruti Chintalapati, Sriya Yadavalli, Subha Senthil Kumar, Sridhar Kejriwal (2023). *The impact of Social Media on College Students of Bangalore*. International Journal of Research Publications and Reviews.
35. Sharma, A., & Sharma, N. (2016). A Study on the Use of Social Media for Educational Purposes by Graduate Students in Haryana. *Journal of Advanced Research in Library and Information Science, 3*(1), 9–16.
36. Sourabh Sharma, Ramesh Behl (2022). *Analysing the Impact of Social Media on Students' Academic Performance: A Comparative Study of Extraversion and Introversive Personality*. Psychological Studies (Vol. 67, Issue 4, pp. 549–559). Springer.
37. Sonia Livingstone, Giovanna Mascheroni, Michael Dreier, Stephane Chaudron, Kate Lagae (2015). *How parents of young children manage digital devices at home: The role of income, education and parental style*. Social Science Research, 63, 222-232.
38. Stefania Manca, Maria Ranieri (2016). *Facebook and the others. Potentials and obstacles of social media for teaching in higher education*. Computers & Education, 95, 216-230.
39. Suraya Hamid, Jenny Waycott, Sherah Kurnia, Shanton Chang, S. (2018). *Understanding students' perceptions of the benefits of Facebook for teaching and learning*. Internet and Higher Education, 37, 20-30.
40. Tarek A. El-Badawy, Yasmin Hashem (2015). *The Impact of Social Media on the Academic Development of School Students*. International Journal of Business Administration
41. Victor Ndubuaku, Victor Inim, Ufodiama Clifford Ndudi, UdoEmmanuel Samuel, Abner Ishaku Prince (2020). *Effect of Social Networking Technology Addiction on Academic Performance of University Students in Nigeria*. International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTEE)

42. Xiaopan Xu, Wanqu Han, Qingqi Liu (2023). *Peer pressure and adolescent mobile social media addiction: Moderation analysis of self-esteem and self-concept clarity*. Digital Public Health, Frontiers in Public Health.
43. Jin Zhao, Ting Jia, Xiuming Wang, Yiming Xiao and Xingqu Wu (2022). *Risk Factors Associated with Social Media Addiction: An Exploratory Study*. Frontiers in Psychology, 13.